
UV-Spectroscopic Analysis and *In vitro* Equivalence Study of Generic Paracetamol Tablets under Biowaiver Conditions

Edebi N. Vaikosen*, Samuel J. Bunu, Raji O. Rafiu, Chukwudi V. Eze

Department of Pharmaceutical and Medicinal Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
E-mail: edebivaikosen@gmail.com

Abstract

The current study aimed to determine the *in vitro* equivalence of generic paracetamol tablets applying UV-spectroscopic analysis and biowaiver settings. *In-vitro* equivalency investigations, including weight uniformity, disintegration, dissolution, hardness, and friability assays, and UV-spectroscopic analysis, were utilized to determine the compliance of various paracetamol brands to the innovator standard. The tablets' hardness ranged from 6.7 ± 0.42 to 9.5 ± 0.33 , with P1 and P5 having the highest and lowest values, respectively. The percentage friability ranged from 0.0294 ± 0.003 to 0.1696 ± 0.01 , with P3 ranking higher than P2, P4, P5, and P1. The brands fell well below the USP-specified limit of $< 1.0\%$. The disintegration time ranged between 6.4 and 9.1 minutes. Within 30 minutes, the dissolution profile showed percentage releases ranging from 79.89 to 87.88%. Except for P2, all brands met the BP criterion for paracetamol, with quantities ranging from 87.17 ± 0.32 to $100.44 \pm 0.17\%$. The innovator brand P5 contained $96.94 \pm 0.33\%$ of the label claim of 500 mg/tablet, while generics ranged from 87.17 ± 0.32 to $100.44 \pm 0.17\%$. There was no significant difference between label claims on brands of paracetamol and computed assay values between the P5 (innovator) and P1, P2, P3, and P4 (generics) in the recovery assay. The RSD and SEM values ranged from 0.17 to 0.37, and 0.49 to 0.96. All of the paracetamol brands examined in this study passed the disintegration test requirements established by the USP and BP, and the procedure can be utilized for routine quality control of solid dose medications.

Keywords: Paracetamol, Fever, Analgesic, Anti-inflammatory, Biowaiver, Equivalence

1. Introduction

Paracetamol is a non-opioid analgesic and antipyretic used to treat fever, mild to moderate pain, and post-surgical discomfort [1-3, 4]. Combining paracetamol with other opioids or non-opioid analgesic medications can augment its pharmacological effects [5]. Paracetamol provides only modest and clinically inconsequential pain relief in osteoarthritis, and there is insufficient evidence to support its use in cancer, low back pain, or neuropathic pain [6-10]. Paracetamol is a safe alternative for patients who cannot tolerate the stomach-irritating side effects of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) [11-13]. Chronic paracetamol use can lead to low hemoglobin levels, indicating inaccurate liver function tests and gastrointestinal hemorrhage [14]. Excessive doses can cause toxicity, including liver failure and paracetamol poisoning. Paracetamol poisoning is a leading cause of acute liver failure in several Western nations [15-17]. It can also result in deadly skin allergies such as toxic epidermal necrolysis and Stevens-Johnson syndrome [18].

Figure 1: Structure of Paracetamol (para-acetaminophen).

Paracetamol appears to exert therapeutic effects by suppressing COX (cyclooxygenase) enzymes and the activity of its metabolite, N-arachidonoylphenolamine (AM404) [19]. When arachidonic acid and peroxide concentrations are low, paracetamol works on cyclooxygenase enzymes in the same way that selective inhibitors of COX-2 do. It is mostly metabolized by the liver by glucuronidation and sulfation, with the resulting metabolites eliminated in the urine. Approximately 2-5% of the medication is eliminated unaltered in urine [22]. UGT1A1 and UGT1A6 glucuronidate paracetamol, account for 50-70% of its metabolism. The SULT1A1, SULT1A3, and SULT1E1 enzymes convert around 25-35% to sulfate [23]. N-acetyl-p-benzoquinone imine (NAPQI) is a hazardous metabolite that results from the cytochrome P450 (CYP2E1) enzymes pathway (5-15%). At average quantities, glutathione can easily metabolize NAPQI, which causes paracetamol-induced liver injury. The non-toxic conjugate APAP-GSH gets absorbed in the bile and transformed into mercapturic and cysteine conjugates, which are eliminated in the urine [23]. The last process makes use of AM404, which is abundant in animal brains and cerebrospinal fluids of paracetamol users. Fatty acid amide hydrolase in the brain transforms 4-aminophenol, another paracetamol metabolite, into AM404 [19, 24]. The cannabinoid system and TRPV1 are critical to paracetamol's analgesic actions, because AM404 stimulates CB1 and CB2 (cannabinoid) receptors, inhibits the endocannabinoid transporter, and activates TRPV1 [19, 25].

When given orally, it is rapidly absorbed in the small intestinal tract but poorly in the stomach. The rate of absorption is controlled by stomach emptying time, which is typically slowed after eating. The highest plasma levels of paracetamol occurred 20 minutes after fasting and 90 minutes after eating. The bioavailability of paracetamol rises with dosage, from 63% at 500 mg to 89% at 1000 mg [22]. The elimination half-life from plasma is between 1.9 and 2.5 hours, with a distribution volume of about 50 L [20]. Protein binding is low, except in cases of overdose, where it might range from 15% to 21%. Following a normal dose, serum concentrations decrease below 200 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). After 4 hours, the drug level often declines to 66 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) [22, 26]. Paracetamol is harmful to a variety of species [27–29]. Paracetamol is sold as a generic medication under several brand names, including Tylenol and Panadol [30]. In 2021, it was one of the most commonly prescribed medications in the United States, with over 5 million prescriptions [31]. The growing quantity of generic pharmaceuticals in the local pharmaceutical market makes it increasingly difficult for patients and physicians to choose the optimal drug [32]. As a result, there is a need to create simple, brief, and low-cost procedures for routinely assessing the in-vitro bioequivalence of medications generally available on the drug market [33-38]. The current study intends to examine the in vitro equivalency of generic paracetamol tablets using UV-spectroscopy and under biowaiver conditions.

2. Materials and Methods

Materials

Reagents and Equipment

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Pure paracetamol powder (99.88%, secondary standard (donated by Primex Nigeria Ltd., Ikeja, Lagos), Sodium hydroxide pellet manufactured by Lobal Chemie Lab reagents Mumbai 400005 India. Hydrochloric acid (37%) manufactured by Riedel-DeHaan Sigma-Aldris chemical Germany, potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate anhydrous 98% manufactured by Loba Chemie PVT LMT, Disodium hydrogen orthophosphate manufactured by J.T Baker USA. All reagents were prepared using distilled water. Spectrumlab 752pro UV-VIS spectrophotometer, analytical weighing balance, spatula, refrigerator, mortar and pestle, test tube, Monsanto hardness tester, friabilator (Erweka friabilator), separating funnel, dissolution tester. Five

brands of Paracetamol coded - P1, P2, P3, P4, and P5 (innovator) were purchased from KETO DEVINE Pharmacy, Amassoma, Bayelsa state. Their brand names, manufacturing dates, expiry dates, batch numbers, NAFDAC numbers, and strength were documented.

Methods

Table 1: *In vitro* Equivalence Study

Test	Methodology
Weight Uniformity Test	Twenty (20) tablets of various brands of paracetamol were weighed separately using an analytical balance (Ohaus Adventure, USA), and the weights were recorded. The average weight and variation were also calculated [39].
Hardness Test	Ten (10) tablets were taken from each batch. The tablet was held within a fixed and movable jaw, and the indicator's reading was adjusted to 0. The force exerted on the tablet's edge was steadily increased by turning the screw knob forward until the tablet broke. The reading was taken from the scale and represents the pressure required in kg/m ² to shatter the tablet [39].
Friability test	Ten tablets of each brand were weighed and abraded individually with a friabilator (ERWEKA, Germany). Following 100 spins, the tablets were weighed. The weight loss showed friability, which was expressed in percentage. The percentage friability should not exceed 1% (w/w) [40]. The friability was estimated by measuring the weight difference using the equation below.
Disintegration test	The disintegration study is critical for evaluating medication release. A disintegration test is used to determine how long it takes for tablets or capsules to disintegrate entirely. Previously, a disintegration test was used to determine the homogeneity of compression characteristics. We now favor this test for optimizing compression qualities. If disintegration time is not uniform, there will be a lack of batch homogeneity and consistency [41].

Determination of maximum wavelength and calibration curve in 0.1M NaOH

To dissolve the powder, 10 mL of 0.1 M NaOH solution was poured into a 100 mL volumetric flask containing 100 mg of paracetamol standard. The 0.1M NaOH solution was then marked. To obtain a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, an aliquot of 0.1mL of the solution was transferred to a 10 mL⁻¹ volumetric flask and filled to the mark with 0.1M NaOH. This was subsequently scanned in the UV range (200-380 nm). The wavelength with the highest absorption was designated as the λ_{max} . Concentrations of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ were obtained from a stock solution of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The absorbance associated with these amounts was determined at the peak wavelength of the resulting spectrum. Absorbance results were utilized to create a calibration curve for calculating the amount of medication in the formulations.

Determination of maximum wavelength and calibration curve in 0.1M HCl

To dissolve the powder, 10 mL of 0.1 M HCl solution was poured into a 100 mL volumetric flask containing 100 mg paracetamol standard. The 0.1M HCl solution was then marked. To obtain a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, an aliquot of 0.1mL of the solution was transferred to a 10 mL⁻¹ volumetric flask and filled to the mark with 0.1M HCl. This was then scanned in the UV range (200-380 nm). The wavelength with the highest absorption was designated as the λ_{max} . Concentrations of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ were generated using a stock solution of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The absorbance of these concentrations was measured at the peak wavelength of the produced spectrum. Absorbance results were utilized to create a calibration curve for measuring the medication released during the dissolving test

Dissolution test and drug release

Dilute HCl (0.1M HCl): To make 0.1M HCl, transfer 8.5 ml concentrated HCl to a 1000 ml volumetric flask holding a tiny amount of water, then add more distilled water to fill the flask to 1000 ml. The dissolution test was performed using the USP Basket method in six replicates for each brand [39]. The dissolution medium was 900 ml of 0.1M HCl maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C. In all tests, 5 mL of dissolving sample was taken at intervals of 0, 5, 10, 15, 30, 45, and 60 minutes and replaced with an equal volume to keep the sink condition. UV spectrophotometry was used to analyze samples after they had been filtered and diluted with the dissolving liquid. The analyte concentration in each aliquot was calculated from a calibration curve [39].

Application of the method to formulated drugs

Paracetamol (10 tablets) was crushed into powder, and an equivalent of 500 mg was weighed into a 100 mL volumetric flask, gently agitated with 30 mL of 0.1M NaOH for 3-5 minutes, and filled to the mark with 0.1M NaOH. After filtering, discard the first 5 mL of the filtrate and transfer aliquots of 100, 200, and 300 μ L to a 100 mL volumetric flask. Dilute to mark with 0.1M NaOH (representing 5, 10, and 15 μ g mL⁻¹). The absorbance of the final solution was measured at 257 nm. The method was repeated for each brand (Innovator and generics), and the percentage content was determined.

Dissolution profile comparison and bioequivalence of generics to innovator brand

The US FDA performance validation test requirements [41] were used to compare the dissolving profiles of innovator and generic pharmaceuticals, together with the USP and BP specified limit of at least 80% of the medication discharged within 30 minutes. Furthermore, the independent model technique of difference factor (f_1) and similarity factor (f_2) was used to examine the dissolution profiles of the generics in comparison to the innovator brand using all-time amplitudes. The FDA and the European Agency for the Evaluation of Medicinal Products (EMA), through the Committee for Proprietary Medicinal Products (CPMP), have accepted the similarity factor f_2 as a criterion for comparing the similarity of two or more dissolution profiles [42]. The use of kinetics - a comparative-dependent model for bioequivalent studies, assuming a first-order kinetic release of active was also adopted.

$$f_1 = \{[\sum_{t=1}^n IR_t - T_t] / [\sum_{t=1}^n R_t]\} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$f_2 = 50 \times \log \left\{ \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{n} \right) \sum_{t=1}^n (R_t - T_t)^2 \right]^{-0.5} \times 100 \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$\log C = \log C_0 - kt / 2.303 \quad (3)$$

Data analysis

The weight uniformity was analyzed using simple statistics, while dissolution profiles of the generics and innovator were done graphically and by calculation using the independent and dependent models. The difference factor (f_1), similarity factor (f_2), and kinetic drug release variables – release rate constant k , half-life ($t_{1/2}$), correlation coefficient (R^2), etc., were determined using Microsoft Excel, 2016.

Results and Discussion

Weight variations give some indication of both good manufacturing procedures (GMP) and the amount of the API (active pharmaceutical ingredient) in the formulation [43]. The hardness test is known to influence disintegration time since it indicates how quickly a tablet disintegrates and the active component is released into a medium, followed by absorption in pharmacokinetics. As a result, proper tablet hardness and ability to resist powdering are necessary for drug quality [44]. The hardness of tablets ranged from 6.7 ± 0.42 to 9.5 ± 0.33 , with P1 and P5

showing the highest and least values respectively (Figure 2). All brands of paracetamol were found satisfactory. The BP requirement for hardness of uncoated tablets ranges from 4 to 10 kg/m².

Figure 2: Hardness of paracetamol tablets

The percentage of friability for Innovator and generic brands is shown in Figure 3. The friability test is used in conjunction with the hardness test to measure the ability of finished drug products to withstand the pressure that emanates from handling, packaging, transportation, and storage [40]. This is largely dependent on the type and quantity of binders and other excipients used in the tablet formulation. Percentage friability ranged from 0.0294 ± 0.003 to 0.1696 ± 0.01 , in the order P3 > P2 > P4 > P5 > P1. All brands of paracetamol were significantly below the USP specified limit of ≤ 1.0 % friability.

Figure 3: Friability of paracetamol tablets.

All brands of paracetamol tablets had disintegration time ranging from 6.4 to 9.1 minutes, this implies that all brands of drug complied with USP/BP specifications for the disintegration test [39, 45].

Figure 4: Disintegration time for innovator and brand paracetamol.

Figure 5 shows the UV absorption spectra for paracetamol in 0.1 M NaOH and 0.1 M HCl solution, with maxima at 257 and 245 nm respectively. The observed maximum for paracetamol in 0.1 M NaOH medium agrees with the maximum stipulated by the BP (2009). Also, the calibration curves were straight-line graphs, with the equation as $Y=0.0724x + 0.0353$, with the correlation coefficient (R^2) being 0.9983 in 0.1 M NaOH, and $Y=0.0816x + 0.1688$, $R^2 = 0.9959$ in 0.1M HCl. These R^2 values depicted good linearity between absorbance and concentration, with Beer's Law obeyed in the concentration range of 2 – 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. In addition, the slope and intercepts were 0.0724 and 0.0353 respectively in 0.1 M NaOH, with corresponding values in 0.1 M HCl being 0.0816 and 0.1688.

Figure 5: UV Spectrum of Paracetamol in 0.1 M NaOH and 0.1M HCl

The therapeutic effectiveness of a dosage form is a function of the amount of drug released into the body fluids, followed by its absorption into the circulatory system [46], thus making the *in-vitro* dissolution (bioequivalence) studies of solid dosage form imperative and by extension determination of the dissolution rate of a dosage form in mimicking the physical action of ingested drugs. Figure 6, shows the dissolution profile of the innovator and the generic brands, with the percentage release of paracetamol ranging from 79.89 – 87.88% within 30 minutes. All brands except P2 (with a percentage release of 79.89% - slightly below the stipulated acceptable minimum of 80%) were considered satisfactory concerning the USP/BP requirements for the dissolution rate of tablet formulation at

t_{30} . This implies that all generic brands except P2 could be considered bioequivalent to Innovator brand P5 [34, 47 - 49].

Figure 6: Dissolution profile of paracetamol brands (Innovator - P5, and generics - P1, P2, P3, and P4)

All brands except P2 complied with the BP specification for solid dosage form paracetamol – as quantities in brands ranged from $87.17 \pm 0.32 - 100.44 \pm 0.17\%$. The BP specification for paracetamol tablets ranges from 95 to 105%. [39]. The innovator brand A5 was found to contain $96.94 \pm 0.33\%$ of the label claim per tablet, while the content of paracetamol in the P2 brand was found to be $87.17 \pm 0.32\%$. This corroborates the recent report on substandard paracetamol in the Nigerian market [50, 51]. The paired t-tests for accuracy and precision between the label claim and amount found in brands ranged from 1.399 – 1.496 (Table 2), while values between P5 (innovator) and generics – P1, P2, P3, and P4 were 1.499, 1.500, 1.441 and 1.489 respectively – all test values were < 3.18 (tabulated) at 95% confidence level for 3 replicates. This suggested that no significant difference between label claims on brands of paracetamol and calculated assay values, in addition, there is a difference between the P5 (innovator) and P1, P2, P3, and P4 (generics) respectively in the recovery assay. Furthermore, the relative standard deviation (%RSD, $n = 3$) and standard error of the mean (SEM) ranged from 0.17 to 0.37 and 0.49 to 0.96 respectively, with the least values recorded by the innovator brand for both properties. These values indicated high reproducibility and reliability, with satisfactory precision and accuracy of method.

Table 1: Assay of different brands of Paracetamol

Sample ID	Label claim (mg/tablet)	Amt found \pm Sd(mg/tablet)	%RSD	SEM	Drug Content (%)
P1	500	482.84 ± 1.63	0.34	0.94	96.57 ± 0.33
P2	500	435.84 ± 1.60	0.37	0.92	87.17 ± 0.32
P3	500	502.18 ± 0.87	0.17	0.50	100.44 ± 0.17
P4	500	484.72 ± 1.66	0.34	0.96	96.94 ± 0.33
P5	500	499.42 ± 0.85	0.17	0.49	99.78 ± 0.17

Table 2: Paired t-test of label claim/Brands and Innovator/Generic Brands

	BRANDS OF PARACETAMOL				
	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5
Label Claim(500 mg/tablet)	$t = 1.496$	$t = 1.460$	$t = 1.408$	$t = 1.490$	$t = 1.399$
Innovator (P5)	$t = 1.499$	$t = 1.500$	$t = 1.441$	$t = 1.498$	Nil
Sample size (n)	3	3	3	3	3
Tabulated t-value	3.18	3.18	3.18	3.18	3.18

Calculated f_1 and f_2 values for the *in vitro* dissolution profile (Table 3) ranged from 6.35 - 11.24 and 99.14 - 110.16 respectively. In applying this independent model, two dissolution profiles are considered similar and bioequivalent, only if the f_1 value lies between 0 and 15, while f_2 must be between 50 and 100 [41]. This implies that all generic brands were comparable to the innovator brand, concerning the difference factor f_1 , while for similarity factor f_2 , three of the profiles (P1, P3, and P4) were considered comparable to the innovator brand P5. The f_2 values for P2 were > 100 . However, some researchers/scientists think that the similarity factor f_2 is a biased and conservative estimate, which does not consider the dissolution differences between innovator and generic brands and the unequal time amplitudes during sampling [52, 53].

Figure 7: Drug release rate constant per time amplitude ($t_5, t_{10}, t_{15}, t_{30}, t_{45}, t_{60}$) (1^{st} order kinetics)

Table 3: *In vitro* kinetic variables for innovator and generic brands

Sample code	Dependent model			Independent model	
	Release rate const. (k) (%.min ⁻¹)	Half-life ($t_{1/2}$)(min)	Correlation coefficient (R^2)	f_1	f_2
P1	5.69×10^{-2}	12.18	0.7215	6.70	99.4
P2	4.96×10^{-2}	13.97	0.7100	11.2	110.1
P3	5.07×10^{-2}	13.67	0.7612	4	6
P4	5.59×10^{-2}	12.40	0.7617	7.17	100.3
P5	6.49×10^{-2}	10.68	0.8037	2	9
				-	-

Also, a comparative dependent model for bioequivalent studies was applied by assuming first-order kinetics [54], with the drug release rate constant k calculated iteratively. The *in vitro* drug release constant k for paracetamol over a six-time amplitude ($t_5 - t_{60}$) ranges from $(4.96 - 6.49) \times 10^{-1}$ (%.min⁻¹) (Table 3), while half-life ($t_{1/2}$) – time taken for 50% of the drug's label claim to be released, was from 10.68 – 13.97 minutes. The correlation coefficients R^2 were all ≥ 0.7100 and implied a strong correlation between the amount of drug released and time. The order of the drug release was $P5 > P1 > P4 > P3 > P2$, respectively.

Conclusion

The weight uniformity, hardness, friability, and disintegration time of all paracetamol brands examined in this study met the USP/BP standards. The dissolution profiles of the innovator and generic brands were found satisfactory, except for brand P2, which had a percentage release slightly less than the permitted requirement of 80% at t_{30} . Based on the in-vitro drug release profile, all generic brands except P2 may be regarded as bioequivalent to Innovator brand P5. There was no significant difference between label claims for paracetamol brands and estimated assay values, nor was there a significant difference between P5 and P1, P2, P3, and P4 (generics) in the recovery assay. The RSD and SEM results indicated strong reproducibility and dependability, as well as satisfactory procedure precision and accuracy. All generic products were comparable to the innovator brand in terms of difference factor f_1 , whereas two of the profiles (P1 and P3) were regarded as comparable to the innovator brand P5. Thus, this method can serve as a routine check for solid-dose pharmaceutical quality control.

References

- [1]. Stephens G, Derry S, Moore RA (2016). Paracetamol (acetaminophen) for acute treatment of episodic tension-type headache in adults. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2019 (6): CD011889. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD011889.pub2. PMC 6457822. PMID 27306653.
- [2]. Chiumello D, Gotti M, Vergani G (2017). Paracetamol in fever in critically ill patients update. *J Crit Care.* 38: 245–252. doi:10.1016/j.jcrc.2016.10.021. PMID 27992852. S2CID 5815020.
- [3]. Saragiotto BT, Abdel Shaheed C, Maher CG (2019). Paracetamol for pain in adults. *BMJ.* 367: 16693. doi:10.1136/bmj.l6693. PMID 31892511. S2CID 209524643.
- [4]. Bailey E, Worthington HV, van Wijk A, Yates JM, Coulthard P, Afzal Z (2013). Ibuprofen and/or paracetamol (acetaminophen) for pain relief after surgical removal of lower wisdom teeth. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* (12): CD004624. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD004624.pub2. PMID 24338830.
- [5]. Moore PA, Hersh EV (2013). Combining ibuprofen and acetaminophen for acute pain management after third-molar extractions: translating clinical research to dental practice. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 144 (8): 898–908. doi:10.14219/jada.archive.2013.0207. PMID 23904576.
- [6]. Machado GC, Maher CG, Ferreira PH, Pinheiro MB, Lin CW, Day RO, (2015). Efficacy and safety of paracetamol for spinal pain and osteoarthritis: systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized placebo-controlled trials. *BMJ.* 350: h1225. doi:10.1136/bmj.h1225. PMC 4381278. PMID 25828856.
- [7]. Saragiotto BT, Machado GC, Ferreira ML, Pinheiro MB, Abdel Shaheed C, Maher CG (2016). Paracetamol for low back pain. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 6 (6): CD012230. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD012230. PMC 6353046. PMID 27271789.
- [8]. Wiffen PJ, Derry S, Moore RA, McNicol ED, Bell RF, Carr DB, (2017). Oral paracetamol (acetaminophen) for cancer pain. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 7 (2): CD012637. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD012637.pub2. PMC 6369932. PMID 28700092.
- [9]. Wiffen PJ, Knaggs R, Derry S, Cole P, Phillips T, Moore RA (2016). Paracetamol (acetaminophen) with or without codeine or dihydrocodeine for neuropathic pain in adults. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 12 (5): CD012227. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD012227.pub2. PMC 6463878. PMID 28027389.
- [10]. Kolasinski SL, Neogi T, Hochberg MC, Oatis C, Guyatt G, Block J, (2020). 2019 American College of Rheumatology/Arthritis Foundation Guideline for the Management of Osteoarthritis of the Hand, Hip, and Knee. *Arthritis Care & Research.* 72 (2): 149–162. doi:10.1002/acr.24131. hdl:2027.42/153772. PMID 31908149. S2CID 210043648.
- [11]. Bally M, Dendukuri N, Rich B, Nadeau L, Helin-Salmivaara A, Garbe E, (2017). Risk of acute myocardial infarction with NSAIDs in real-world use: bayesian meta-analysis of individual patient data. *The BMJ.* 357: j1909. doi:10.1136/bmj.j1909. PMC 5423546. PMID 28487435.
- [12]. Lanas A, Chan FK (2017). Peptic ulcer disease. *The Lancet.* 390 (10094): 613–624. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(16)32404-7. PMID 28242110. S2CID 4547048.

- [13]. Conaghan PG, Arden N, Avouac B, Migliore A, Rizzoli R (2019). Safety of Paracetamol in Osteoarthritis: What Does the Literature Say?. *Drugs Aging*. 36 (Suppl 1): 7–14. doi:10.1007/s40266-019-00658-9. PMC 6509082. PMID 31073920.
- [14]. Roberts E, Delgado Nunes V, Buckner S, Latchem S, Constanti M, Miller P, (2016). Paracetamol: not as safe as we thought? A systematic literature review of observational studies. *Ann Rheum Dis*. 75 (3): 552–9. doi:10.1136/annrheumdis-2014-206914. PMC 4789700. PMID 25732175.
- [15]. Larson AM, Polson J, Fontana RJ, Davern TJ, Lalani E, Hynan LS, (2005). Acetaminophen-induced acute liver failure: results of a United States multicenter, prospective study. *Hepatology*. 42 (6): 1364–72. doi:10.1002/hep.20948. PMID 16317692. S2CID 24758491.
- [16]. Hawkins LC, Edwards JN, Dargan PI (2007). Impact of restricting paracetamol pack sizes on paracetamol poisoning in the United Kingdom: a review of the literature. *Drug Saf*. 30 (6): 465–79. doi:10.2165/00002018-200730060-00002. PMID 17536874. S2CID 36435353.
- [17]. Daly FF, Fountain JS, Murray L, Graudins A, & Buckley NA (2008). Guidelines for the management of paracetamol poisoning in Australia and New Zealand—explanation and elaboration. A consensus statement from clinical toxicologists consulting with the Australasian poison information centers. *The Medical Journal of Australia*. 188 (5): 296–301. doi:10.5694/j.1326-5377.2008.tb01625.x. PMID 18312195. S2CID 9505802.
- [18]. FDA (2019). FDA Drug Safety Communication: The FDA warns of rare but serious skin reactions with the pain reliever/fever reducer acetaminophen. U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA). 1 August 2013. Archived from the original on 28 October 2019. Retrieved 27 October 2019.
- [19]. Ghanem CI, Pérez MJ, Manautou JE, Mottino AD (2016). Acetaminophen from liver to brain: New insights into drug pharmacological action and toxicity. *Pharmacological Research*. 109: 119–31. doi:10.1016/j.phrs.2016.02.020. PMC 4912877. PMID 26921661.
- [20]. Graham GG, Davies MJ, Day RO, Mohamudally A, Scott KF (2013). The modern pharmacology of paracetamol: therapeutic actions, mechanism of action, metabolism, toxicity, and recent pharmacological findings. *Inflammopharmacology*. 21 (3): 201–32. doi:10.1007/s10787-013-0172-x. PMID 23719833. S2CID 11359488.
- [21]. Bunu JS, Miediegha O, Awala EV, Alfred-Ugbenbo D, Baba H, Usifoh CO (2024). Synthesis and In Silico Analysis of Chalcone Derivatives as Potential Prostaglandin Synthetase Inhibitors. *Biomed J Sci & Tech Res*, 55(2)-2024. 46709 - 46720. DOI: 10.26717/BJSTR.2024.55.008662.
- [22]. Forrest JA, Clements JA, Prescott LF (1982). Clinical pharmacokinetics of paracetamol. *Clin Pharmacokinet*. 7 (2): 93–107. doi:10.2165/00003088-198207020-00001. PMID 7039926. S2CID 20946160.
- [23]. McGill MR, Jaeschke H (2013). Metabolism and disposition of acetaminophen: recent advances in relation to hepatotoxicity and diagnosis. *Pharm Res*. 30 (9): 2174–87. doi:10.1007/s11095-013-1007-6. PMC 3709007. PMID 23462933.
- [24]. Sharma CV, Long JH, Shah S, Rahman J, Perrett D, Ayoub SS, (2017). First evidence of the conversion of paracetamol to AM404 in human cerebrospinal fluid. *J Pain Res*. 10: 2703–2709. doi:10.2147/JPR.S143500. PMC 5716395. PMID 29238213.
- [25]. Ohashi N, Kohno T (2020). Analgesic Effect of Acetaminophen: A Review of Known and Novel Mechanisms of Action. *Front Pharmacol*. 11: 580289. doi:10.3389/fphar.2020.580289. PMC 7734311. PMID 33328986.
- [26]. Marx J, Walls R, Hockberger R (2013). *Rosen's Emergency Medicine – Concepts and Clinical Practice*. Elsevier Health Sciences. ISBN 9781455749874.
- [27]. Maddison JE, Page SW, Church D (2002). *Small Animal Clinical Pharmacology*. Elsevier Health Sciences. pp. 260–1. ISBN 978-0702025730.
- [28]. Allen AL (2003). The diagnosis of acetaminophen toxicosis in a cat. *The Canadian Veterinary Journal*. 44 (6): 509–10. PMC 340185. PMID 12839249.

- [29]. van den Hurk P, Kerckamp HM (2019). Phylogenetic origins for severe acetaminophen toxicity in snake species compared to other vertebrate taxa. *Comp Biochem Physiol C Toxicol Pharmacol*. 215: 18–24. doi:10.1016/j.cbpc.2018.09.003. PMID 30268769. S2CID 52890371.
- [30]. Hamilton RJ (2013). *Tarascon pocket pharmacopoeia : 2013 classic shirt-pocket edition (27th ed.)*. Burlington, Massachusetts: Jones & Bartlett Learning. p. 12. ISBN 9781449665869. Archived from the original on 8 September 2017.
- [31]. ClinCalc (2024). The Top 300 of 2021. *ClinCalc*. Archived from the original on 15 January 2024. Retrieved 14 January 2024.
- [32]. Vaikosen, EN, Bunu, SJ, Santus, SK, Balogun, OD, & Nyalas-Omeire D. (2024). Quality Assurance and In-vitro Bioequivalence Analysis of Amlodipine Besylate Tablets. *Asian Journal of Chemical Sciences*, 14(2), 169–179. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajocs/2024/v14i2302>.
- [33]. Bunu JS, Vaikosen NE, & Nnadozie WK, (2020). Chloroquine Phosphate Metabolism and Gender-based Phenotypic Analysis in Healthy Subjects Urine Following Oral Administration. *Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Research*; 6 (Special Issue on COVID-19):37-44. 25. Doi: 10.18502/pbr.v6i(s1).4400.
- [34]. Ebeshi UB, Bunu JS, Kpun HF, & Ezebube CO (2022). Analysis of gastrointestinal acid-neutralizing potency of some commercial antacid tablet formulations. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 19(02), 008–013. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2022.19.2.0159>.
- [35]. Bunu JS, Alfred-Ugbenbo D, Dode E, & Lambert FK (2023). In-vitro bioequivalence analysis of some Artemether-Lumefantrine-based combination Formulations utilized in Nigeria. *Mod App in pharmacy & Pharma Sci* 1(1); 23-29. MS.ID.000104.
- [36]. Dode E, Bunu JS, & Garando OR (2023). Assessment of different brands of diclofenac tablets: An evaluation utilizing UV spectroscopy and disintegration test methods. *World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences*, 14(02), 001–006. DOI: 10.30574/wjbps.2023.14.2.0201.
- [37]. Ebeshi UB, Bunu JS, Egemba CL, Vaikosen EN, & Kashimawo A, (2023). Evaluation of Stability and TLC Fingerprinting of the Artemether Component in Artemether-Lumefantrine Combination Suspension Formulations Available in Nigeria Pharmaceutical Market. *Asian Journal of Research in Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 12(4);183-190. DOI: 10.9734/ajrimps/2023/v12i4241.
- [38]. Vaikosen EN, Bunu JS, Dode E, & Efidi RB (2023). Spectrophotometric fingerprinting and chemical determination of streptomycin, amikacin, neomycin, and gentamycin sulphate by condensing with ninhydrin reagent. *International Journal of Chemistry Research*, 7(3); 5-10.
- [39]. *British Pharmacopoeia* (2009). <https://www.pharmacopoeia.com/the-bp/how-to-use>.
- [40]. *United States Pharmacopeia and National Formulary (USP 43–NF 38)*. Rockville, MD: United States Pharmacopeial Convention; 2020.
- [41]. FDA (2008). *Guidance for Industry Orally Disintegrating Tablets* U.S. Department of Health and Human Services Food and Drug Administration Center for Drug Evaluation and Research (CDER). 2008.
- [42]. Diaz, D. A., Colgan, S. T., Langer, C. S., Bandi, N. T., Likar, M. D., & Van Alstine, L. (2016). Dissolution Similarity Requirements: How Similar or Dissimilar Are the Global Regulatory Expectations?. *The AAPS journal*, 18(1), 15–22. <https://doi.org/10.1208/s12248-015-9830-9>.
- [43]. Nally, J.D., ed. (2007). *Good Manufacturing Practices for Pharmaceuticals (6th ed.)*. CRC Press. p. 424. ISBN 9781420020939.
- [44]. Joseph Price Remington (2006). *Remington: The Science and Practice of Pharmacy*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. ISBN 0781746736.
- [45]. Ghourichay, M. P., Kiaie, S. H., Nokhodchi, A., Javadzadeh, Y. (2021). Formulation and Quality Control of Orally Disintegrating Tablets (ODTs): Recent Advances and Perspectives. *BioMed research international*, 2021, 6618934. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6618934>.
- [46]. Stielow, M., Witczyńska, A., Kubryń, N., Fijałkowski, Ł., Nowaczyk, J., & Nowaczyk, A. (2023). The Bioavailability of Drugs-The Current State of Knowledge. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 28(24), 8038. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28248038>.

- [47]. Bunu JS, V Aniako, VP Karade, EN Vaikosen, BU Ebeshi (2023), Thin-Layer Chromatographic and UV-Spectrophotometric Analysis of Frequently Utilized Oral Macrolide Antibiotics, *International Journal in Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 1(9), 265-274. Doi:10.5281/zenodo.8340601.
- [48]. Dode E, D Alfred-Ugbenbo, Bunu JS, & Marcus A (2023). Physicochemical analysis and quality assessment of Lisinopril oral formulations used in the management of hypertension. *International Journal of Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences Archive*, 05(02), 043–048. DOI: 10.53771/ijbpsa.2023.5.2.0036.
- [49]. Oraeluno JN, Obasi JC, Bunu JS, Bamigbola E, Vaikosen, EN, Igwe, FU (2023). In vitro quality assessment of five different brands of cefuroxime axetil suspension sold in Amassoma, Nigeria. *Journal of Biological Pharmaceutical and Chemical Research*, 10(3): 31-39.
- [50]. Adekunle M. (2024). Pharmaceutical Society of Nigeria (PSN), demises report on substandard local paracetamols. Available at: <https://guardian.ng/news/psn-dismisses-report-on-substandard-local-paracetamols/>. Accessed 08 April 2024.
- [51]. NAFDAC (2024). National Agency for Food, Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) Disputes Report on Substandard Paracetamol Tablets in Nigeria. Available at: <https://www.rootstv.ng/news/2024/01/nafdac-disputes-report-on-substandard-paracetamol-tablets-in-nigeria/>. Accessed 08 April 2024.
- [52]. Al-Jazairi, A. S., Bhareth, S., Eqtefan, I. S., Al-Suwayeh, S. A. (2008). Brand and generic medications: are they interchangeable?. *Annals of Saudi Medicine*, 28(1), 33–41. <https://doi.org/10.5144/0256-4947.2008.33>.
- [53]. Kassaye, L., Genete, G. (2013). Evaluation and comparison of in-vitro dissolution profiles for different brands of amoxicillin capsules. *African Health Sciences*, 13(2), 369–375. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v13i2.25>.
- [54]. Gwaza, L., Gordon, J., Potthast, H., Welink, J., Leufkens, H., Stahl, M., & García-Arieta, A. (2015). Influence of point estimates and study power of bioequivalence studies on establishing bioequivalence between generics by adjusted indirect comparisons. *European journal of clinical pharmacology*, 71(9), 1083–1089. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00228-015-1889-9>.

